

FORMATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Phraseological units are considered as important elements both in speech and written forms. Therefore, the article aims to investigate the phraseological units of English language and its formation. The result of the research depicts that the formation of phraseological units has been investigated by scholars and the article deals with the examples of ways of forming phraseological units in English language.

The term "phraseology" is derived from the Greek words phrasis-speech and logos-teaching. This term denotes a section of linguistics that is devoted to the study of the phraseological composition of the language, i.e. the subject of this science is the semantic, morphological and stylistic properties of phraseological units[4.307-328].

Phraseology is also called a set of phraseological units inherent in a particular language, any writer or literary work. Phraseology deals with the study of the phraseological composition of the language [6]. Phraseology is engaged in the development of methods for the study of phraseological units, their selection, classification and phraseography - descriptions in dictionaries. This science is studying the primary, original forms and meanings of phraseological units, determining their sources for all available monuments. She also tries to

identify the spheres of their use in different eras of the existence of the language, as well as to establish the volumes of the phraseological composition and the system of ordering in a particular historical epoch of the development of the language[1].

In a phraseological system, the language is a phraseological unit. Stable phrases or expressionism provide unified combinations of words that have a single integral meaning and perform one syntactic function.

The stability of a phraseological combination is understood as the lexical composition assigned to it, and expressiveness is the presence of an emotional and evaluative coloration. These phrases are used in speech in the form of a ready-made lexical unit and having a general meaning, which often has little meaning in it [6].

The formation of phraseological units usually occurs on a figurative-

metaphorical basis, which is why it can be argued that phraseological units are actively involved in the formation of the linguistic picture of the world and national cultures. [3]. The analysis of the figurative-motivational foundations helps to reveal the national culture in PU, since phraseological units, as already noted above, reflect the mentality of the people.

As L.I. Roizenon, E.A. Malinovsky, A.D. Khayutin, "in a number of works it is exclusively about the term" phraseology", the terms" idioms ", " idioms "are completely absent. It is characteristic that the examples given in these studies indicate that phraseology is understood as both idioms and expressions of a terminological nature, proverbial sayings and even literary cliches and reminiscences " [4.307-328].

A.V. Kunin distinguishes seven main types of phraseologicalization depending on the linguistic material, which formed the basis of the future phrase, preceding the stage of potential phraseology, and the method of its phraseologicalization, taking into account both linguistic and extra linguistic factors:

- 1) the formation of a phrase by reinterpreting variable word combinations;
- 2) the formation of phrases by reinterpreting stable combinations of non-phraseological nature;
- 3) the formation of phraseological expressions on the basis of potential phraseological units;
- 4) formation of phrases from the author's phrases;
- 5) formation of phrases on the basis of the plot, but not the combination of words;

6) formation of the phrases by puns of homonyms;

7) formation of the phrases from the phrases (phraseological derivation) [5.9]. In terms of syntactic functions among the stable combinations of phraseological units are distinguished: [1]

1) Verbal (verbal, i.e. performing the role of a verb): to bear/ carry the cross, to act/ play the fool, to touch the ark, to curse the day, to spring from somebody's loins, to stink in somebody's nostrils, to spring from the loins of somebody, to stink in the nostrils of somebody, to lie at the door of somebody, to strengthen somebody's hands / strengthen the hand of somebody, : take a bull by the horns, reel in fishing rods, get out of the water dry, hang up your nose, plug someone in the belt, wiggle your brains, break wood, forget the way to someone

2) Substantive (performing the role of a noun): angel's visits, apple-pie order, ...she was in revolt against an apple-pie order of existence which was being forced upon her (Th.Dreiser,K.,673), Captain of industry, a change of heart, When recently he had announced his intention of "turning Catholic", his wife was delighted at Ted's change of heart, little suspecting his real motives, a break in the clouds, a bull in a china shop, a lay of the land, "Yes, - he said succinctly, - see the lay of that land, but what do I get out of it?" (Th.Dreiser, K., 554). Cupboard love, the dregs of society, scapegoat, neither fish nor meat, cornerstone, storm in a glass of water, Achilles' heel, sodom and gomorrah, beating of babies

3) Adjectival (performing the role of an adjective): easy-going, not sewn with bast like a cucumber, of a middle hand, out of this world, under the fly, unclean, blood

with milk, in seventh heaven, on one's mind high and mighty, spick and span, brand new, safe and sound, (as) cool as a cucumber, (as) nervous as a cat, (as) weak as a kitten, (as) good as gold (usually spoken about children), (as) pretty as a picture, as large as life, (as) slippery as an eel, (as) thick as thieves, (as) drunk as an owl (sl.), (as) mad as a hatter/a hare in March.

4) Adverbial (fulfilling the role of an adverb): close at hand, head over heels, head over to it, hand in hand, at every step, to smithereens, like a ram to a new gate, at random, reluctantly, at all blades, under the curtain, high and low (as in They searched for him high and low), by hook or by crook, for love or money, in cold, in the dead of night, between the devil and the deep sea, to the bitter end, by a long chalk.

5) Interjective (fulfilling the role of an interjection): My God/ By Jove! ByGeorge! Goodness gracious! GoodHeavens! (Worrall , 2010: 38), "Good God!", "God damn it". Good wishes, goodbyes. Good day! Good afternoon !, How are you getting on? Victory be yours !; I wish you very success! Bully for you !; Well done !, Bravo !, Great! !; Good business! Wow !; You will not say anything! Merry Christmas !; A glad New Year! Three cheers for our visitors !; Long live the guests! Here's how! For your health! Happy landings! Have a nice flight!

Conclusion. Taking into account the above-given data it can be concluded that phraseological units are essential parts of phraseology. The ways of forming phraseological units depend on the elements in the word combinations. Therefore, the article presented the core ways of forming phraseological units.

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